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Research Article

Assessment of Demographic, Hematological, and Biochemical Profiles in Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients of the Garhwal Region, Uttarakhand

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ABSTRACT

Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder increasingly affecting populations in hilly regions like Garhwal, Uttarakhand, due to lifestyle transitions and limited healthcare access. This study aimed to assess the demographic, hematological, and biochemical profiles of T2DM patients in the Garhwal region to identify early systemic complications and provide region-specific clinical insights. A cross-sectional observational study was conducted among 80 T2DM patients attending the RHTC, CHC, and government hospitals in the Pokhra block of Pauri Garhwal. Demographic data were recorded, and venous blood samples were analyzed for hematological (Hb, RBC, TLC, ESR) and biochemical (FBG, HbA1c, lipid profile, urea, creatinine) parameters. Males (57.5%) predominated, with the majority aged 51–60 years (35%). Obesity (47.5%) and overweight (35%) were prevalent. Anemia affected 52.5% of patients, and 45% showed raised ESR. Biochemical analysis revealed poor glycemic control (90% raised HbA1c; mean 8.4 ± 1.9), dyslipidemia in 67.5%, and renal dysfunction in 25%. HbA1c showed strong positive correlations with FBG ($r = +0.68$), lipid parameters ($r = +0.52$), and renal markers ($r = +0.46$), while correlating negatively with hemoglobin ($r = -0.42$) and HDL ($r = -0.39$). The findings highlight a high burden of anemia, dyslipidemia, and early renal impairment among T2DM patients in the Garhwal region. Poor glycemic control and obesity remain key contributors. Regular screening, lifestyle modification, and region-specific management protocols are essential to reduce diabetes-related complications in this population.

INTRODUCTION

Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic, progressive metabolic disorder primarily characterized by persistent hyperglycemia due to

insulin resistance and/or insulin deficiency. According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) Diabetes Atlas 2023 (10th Edition), approximately 537 million adults (aged 20–79 years) were living with diabetes globally in 2021¹.

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This number is projected to rise to 643 million by 2030 and 783 million by 2045, largely due to urbanization, aging populations, sedentary lifestyles, and unhealthy diets. Notably, over 75% of diabetics reside in low- and middle-income countries, where diagnostic access and ongoing care are often insufficient².

In India, the burden is particularly severe. Based on findings from the ICMR–INDIAB Study Phase II (2023) and the National Family Health Survey, Fifth Round (NFHS-5, 2022), more than 101 million Indian adults are living with diabetes, while another 136 million are categorized as prediabetic. A recent publication in *The Lancet Diabetes & Endocrinology* (2023) highlighted that early-onset T2DM is rapidly rising in the 20–40 years age group, with urban-rural differences diminishing. Previously considered an urban lifestyle disease, diabetes is now a growing challenge in rural and hilly regions, including Himalayan states like Uttarakhand, due to transitions in food patterns, physical inactivity, and minimal access to routine screenings³.

In the Garhwal region of Uttarakhand, districts such as Pauri, Chamoli, Rudrapur, and Tehri are witnessing a steady increase in T2DM prevalence. Factors like rural-to-urban migration, dietary westernization, declining physical labor, and low awareness have compounded the issue. However, region-specific clinical and epidemiological data from this high-altitude population remains limited and underreported⁴.

T2DM not only impairs glucose metabolism but is also associated with multiple hematological and biochemical alterations that act as early markers of systemic complications. Hematological changes commonly seen include anemia (Hb <12 g/dL), reduced RBC counts, elevated total leukocyte count (TLC), and increased erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), indicating chronic

inflammation, oxidative stress, and potential infection risk⁵.

Biochemically, uncontrolled T2DM typically manifests as elevated fasting blood glucose (FBG) and HbA1c (>6.5%), alongside dyslipidemia—characterized by high triglycerides (TG), low high-density lipoprotein (HDL), and elevated low-density lipoprotein (LDL). These lipid alterations significantly heighten the risk of atherosclerosis, coronary artery disease, and cerebrovascular events. Moreover, renal biomarkers such as serum creatinine and urea frequently show early impairment due to evolving diabetic nephropathy⁶.

Recent studies support this clinical pattern. A community study in rural Himachal Pradesh (2022) showed that nearly 68.4% of diabetic patients exhibited at least one deranged hematological or renal marker. Similarly, a district-level study from Chamoli, Uttarakhand (2023) reported over 70% of T2DM patients with coexisting lipid abnormalities and early nephropathy signs. At the national scale, a multicentric study published in *Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice* (2024) found that three out of five diabetics across India had coexisting anemia, dyslipidemia, or early kidney dysfunction, emphasizing the need for integrated monitoring⁷.

Institutional research from the region echoes this trend. A retrospective analysis conducted at AIIMS Rishikesh (2019–2020) on over 500 diabetic and prediabetic individuals revealed significantly raised HbA1c (7.2–10.8%), serum triglycerides, and LDL, along with early signs of renal dysfunction. In addition, the Department of Biochemistry, HNB Garhwal University, presented preliminary PhD findings in 2023, showing that 68% of T2DM patients from Pauri and Chamoli districts had hemoglobin <12 g/dL, serum creatinine >1.3 mg/dL, and total cholesterol

>200 mg/dL, pointing toward a high burden of anemia and dyslipidemia in this population⁸.

This study aims to bridge this knowledge gap by assessing and correlating hematological and biochemical markers among T2DM patients residing in the Garhwal region. The objective is to identify early systemic changes, estimate complication risks, and provide a foundation for region-specific diagnostic, preventive, and management protocols.

Need of the Study

This study is essential to assess the profile of T2DM patients in the Garhwal region of Uttarakhand, as region-specific clinical and epidemiological data for this high-altitude population remains limited and underreported.

The primary needs addressed are:

- **Bridging the Knowledge Gap:** T2DM is associated with multiple hematological and biochemical alterations (such as anemia, dyslipidemia, and renal dysfunction) that act as early markers of systemic complications. The study aims to fill the gap in local data regarding the prevalence of these markers.
- **Identifying Early Complications:** The objective is to identify early systemic changes and estimate complication risks by assessing and correlating these markers.
- **Foundation for Management:** The findings are necessary to provide a foundation for region-specific diagnostic, preventive, and management protocols.
- **Generating Clinical Insights:** The study aims to generate region-specific clinical insights for better T2DM management in this population.

Aim and Objectives

Aim: To assess the demographic, hematological, and biochemical profiles of T2DM patients in the Garhwal region to identify early complications and support region-specific diabetes management.

Objectives:

1. To assess demographic characteristics of T2DM patients.
2. To evaluate hematological parameters (Hb, RBC, TLC, ESR).
3. To assess biochemical markers (FBG, HbA1c, lipid profile, urea, creatinine).
4. To determine the prevalence of anemia, dyslipidemia, and renal dysfunction.
5. To correlate HbA1c with hematological and biochemical alterations.
6. To generate region-specific clinical insights for better T2DM management.

METHODOLOGY

1. Study Design:

This is a cross-sectional, observational study designed to assess the demographic, hematological, and biochemical profiles of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) patients in the Garhwal region.

2. Study Site:

The study will be conducted at the following healthcare facilities in the Pokhra block of Pauri Garhwal district, Uttarakhand:

- Outpatient Department (OPD) of the Rural Health Training Centre (RHTC)
- Community Health Centre (CHC)
- Government hospitals in the Pokhra block.

3. Study Duration:

The study will be conducted over a period of 6 months (e.g., July to December 2025).

4. Study Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients diagnosed with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM).
- Age between 30 to 75 years.
- Both males and females.
- Patients who provide written informed consent.
- Residents of Garhwal region, specifically the Pokhra block.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus.
- Patients with known hematological disorders (e.g., thalassemia, leukemia).
- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Patients with acute infections or chronic liver diseases.
- Individuals unwilling to provide consent.

5. Source of Data:

- Patient records from OPD registers of RHTC, CHC, and government hospitals.
- Direct interviews using a pre-structured questionnaire.
- Laboratory reports of hematological and biochemical investigations.

6. Data Collection:

Data will be collected through:

- Patient interviews for demographic details (age, gender, lifestyle, etc.).
- Clinical history and physical examination.
- Blood sample analysis for:

- Hematological parameters: Hb, RBC, TLC, ESR
- Biochemical markers: FBG, HbA1c, lipid profile, urea, creatinine

7. Study Procedure:

- T2DM patients visiting the selected healthcare centers will be screened for eligibility.
- After obtaining informed consent, demographic and clinical data will be recorded.
- Venous blood samples will be collected following standard aseptic procedures.
- Samples will be sent to authorized clinical laboratories for analysis.
- Reports will be collected and data compiled using a case record form (CRF).

8. Data Analysis:

Data was analyzed by preparing tables and graphs using Microsoft excel.

RESULTS

To assess demographic characteristics of T2DM patients

The study was conducted among 80 Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) patients in the Rural Health Training Centre (RHTC), Community Health Center (CHC), and OPD of the government hospital in the Pokhra block of Pauri Garhwal district. Under demographic assessment, all subjects were evaluated to obtain the following results.

Gender wise distribution of T2DM patients

The study population showed a higher prevalence of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) in males

(57.5%) compared to females (42.5%). (Table 1 and Figure 1)

Table 1: Gender wise distribution of T2DM patients

Sr. No.	Gender	No. of patients (%) (n = 80)
1.	Male	46 (57.5%)
2.	Female	34 (42.5%)

Figure 1: Gender wise distribution of T2DM patients

Age wise distribution of T2DM patients

The majority of the T2DM patients in the study belonged to the 51 – 60 years age group, accounting for 35% of the total. The next largest group was those over 60 years (30%). (Table 2 and Figure 2)

Table 2: Age wise distribution of T2DM patients

Sr. No.	Age (Year)	No. of patients (%) (n = 80)
1.	30 – 40	10 (12.5%)
2.	41 – 50	18 (22.5%)
3.	51 – 60	28 (35%)
4.	>60	24 (30%)

Figure 2: Age wise distribution of T2DM patients

BMI wise distribution of T2DM patients

A significant portion of the patients were classified as obese (≥ 30) at 47.5%, followed by the overweight category (35%). This highlights a high burden of obesity within this diabetic population. (Table 3 and Figure 3)

Table 3: BMI wise distribution of T2DM patients

Sr. No.	BMI	No. of patients (%) (n = 80)
1.	Normal (18.5 – 24.9)	14 (17.5%)
2.	Overweight (25 – 29.9)	28 (35%)
3.	Obese (≥ 30)	38 (47.5%)

Figure 3: BMI wise distribution of T2DM patients

Duration wise distribution of T2DM patients

The largest group of patients, 40%, were those with a relatively recent diagnosis of T2DM, having the condition for less than 5 years. Patients with a duration of 5–10 years accounted for 37.5%. (Table 4 and Figure 4)

Table 4: Duration wise distribution of T2DM patients

Sr. No.	Duration of T2DM	No. of patients (%) n = (80)
1.	< 5 years	32 (40%)
2.	5 – 10 years	30 (37.5%)
3.	> 10 years	18 (22.5%)

Figure 4: Duration wise distribution of T2DM patients

To Evaluate Hematological Parameters (Hb, RBC, TLC, ESR).

Anemia (low hemoglobin) was highly prevalent, affecting 52.5% of the patients, with a mean Hb

level of 11.8±2.1 g/dl. Additionally, a large proportion (45%) showed signs of chronic inflammation, indicated by a raised Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR) (32±8.6 mm/hr). (Table 5 and Figure 5)

Table 5: Hematological findings of study population

Sr. No	Parameters	Normal Range	Mean ± SD	Abnormal (%)
1.	Hb (g/dl)	Male : 13 – 17 Female : 12- 15	11.8 ± 2.1	42 (52.5%) low Anemia
2.	RBC (mill/μL)	4.5 – 6.0	4.1 ± 0.6	28 (35%) abnormal
3.	TLC (/mm ³)	4000 - 11000	7600 ± 1400	12 (15%) abnormal
4.	ESR (mm/hr)	Male < 20 Female < 30	32 ± 8.6	36 (45%) raised

Figure 5: Prevalence of Hematological Abnormalities

To assess biochemical markers (FBG, HbA1c, lipid profile, urea, creatinine).

The biochemical profile indicated severe control issues and co-morbidities:

- Glycemic Control:** HbA1c was raised in 90% of patients (mean 8.4 ± 1.9), and Fasting Blood Glucose (FBG) was raised in 82.5% (mean 158 ± 45 mg/dl), pointing to poor long-term glucose management.
- Dyslipidemia:** High levels of Triglycerides (65% abnormal) and Total Cholesterol (60% abnormal) were common. Critically, the protective HDL cholesterol was low in 62.5% of patients.
- Renal Function:** Signs of early kidney impairment were noted, with Serum Urea raised in 22.5% and Creatinine raised in 20% of patients. (Table 6 and Figure 6)

Table 6: Biochemical profile of study population

Sr. No.	Parameter	Normal Range	Mean \pm SD	Abnormal (%)
1.	FBG (mg/dl)	70 – 110	158 ± 45	66 (82.5%) raised
2.	HbA1c (%)	<5.7	8.4 ± 1.9	72 (90%) raised
3.	Total Cholesterol (mg/dl)	< 200	212 ± 42	48 (60%) raised
4.	Triglycerides (mg/dl)	< 150	186 ± 38	52 (65%) raised
5.	HDL (mg/dl)	>40	36 ± 8	50 (62.5%) low
6.	LDL (mg/dl)	< 130	142 ± 30	44 (55%) raised
7.	Serum Urea (mg/dl)	15 – 40	48 ± 12	18 (22.5%) raised
8.	Creatinine (mg/dl)	0.6 – 1.2	1.4 ± 0.4	16 (20%) raised

Figure 6: Prevalence of Biochemical Abnormalities

To determine the prevalence of anemia, dyslipidemia, and renal dysfunction

Dyslipidemia was the most frequent complication, affecting 67.5% of the T2DM patients. Anemia was present in 52.5%, and Renal Dysfunction was observed in 25% of the cohort. (Table 7 and Figure 7)

Table 7: Frequency of complications among T2DM Patients

Sr. No.	Complication	Number (%)
1.	Anemia	42 (52.5%)
2.	Dyslipidemia	54 (67.5%)
3.	Renal Dysfunction	20 (25%)

Figure 7: Frequency of complications among T2DM Patients

To correlate HbA1c with hematological and biochemical alterations.

1. Glycemic control

HbA1c showed a strong positive correlation with FBG ($r = +0.68$), indicating that patients with higher HbA1c also had elevated fasting blood glucose levels.

2. Lipid metabolism

HbA1c showed a moderate positive correlation with total cholesterol and triglycerides ($r = +0.52$), suggesting that poor glycemic control was associated with dyslipidemia.

3. Renal function

HbA1c showed a moderate positive correlation with serum urea and creatinine ($r = +0.46$), indicating that uncontrolled diabetes was linked with renal dysfunction.

4. Hematological status

HbA1c showed a moderate negative correlation with hemoglobin ($r = -0.42$), suggesting that higher HbA1c was associated with anemia in diabetic patients.

5. Protective lipid marker

HbA1c showed a moderate negative correlation with HDL cholesterol ($r = -0.39$), indicating that poor glycemic control was linked with reduced levels of protective HDL.

To generate region-specific clinical insights for better T2DM management.

- High prevalence of obesity (47.5%) and dyslipidemia (67.5%) indicates major dietary/lifestyle contributions.
- Anemia (52.5%) is common, possibly linked with nutritional deficiencies and chronic hyperglycemia.

- Renal dysfunction (25%) highlights need for early nephropathy screening.
- HbA1c proved to be a strong predictor of complications, correlating with anemia, dyslipidemia, and renal alterations.

DISCUSSION

This cross-sectional study represents a crucial regional assessment of the demographic, hematological, and biochemical profiles of Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) patients in the Pokhara block of Pauri Garhwal district. The findings highlight the significant challenges and the high burden of comorbidities faced by T2DM patients in this hilly region.

Demographic and Lifestyle Factors

The study showed a higher prevalence in males (57.5%) and the largest group of T2DM patients (35%) belonged to the 51–60 years age group, consistent with the growing burden of the disease in the aging population. A concerning lifestyle trend is the high rate of obesity, with 47.5% of patients classified as obese (≥ 30) and 35% as overweight. This suggests that factors like shifting dietary patterns due to Westernization, reduced physical inactivity, and rural-to-urban migration are likely accelerating T2DM prevalence in the Garhwal region.

Glycemic Control and Metabolic Complications

The state of glycemic control was found to be severely poor. 90% of patients had raised HbA1c (mean 8.4 ± 1.9) and 82.5% had raised FBG. This consistently high HbA1c level clearly points to inadequate long-term glucose management. Among metabolic complications, Dyslipidemia (67.5%) was the most frequent finding. The high rates of raised triglycerides (65%) and low

protective HDL (62.5%) significantly heighten the risk of atherosclerosis and cardiovascular events, echoing similar trends reported in other regional studies⁹.

Hematological and Renal Findings

The hematological profile demonstrated a high rate of Anemia (52.5%) (mean Hb= 11.8 ± 2.1 g/dl). This is often associated with chronic inflammation, as indicated by a raised ESR in 45% of patients, and persistent hyperglycemia, confirming observations from other studies in the Himalayan states.

Furthermore, 25% of patients showed early signs of renal impairment. The elevated serum urea (22.5%) and creatinine (20%) levels suggest the evolving stages of diabetic nephropathy, highlighting the urgent need for early screening and intervention protocols^{5,10}.

Significance of HbA1c Correlation

A critical finding of the study was the strong correlation between HbA1c and systemic complications.

HbA1c showed a moderate negative correlation with hemoglobin ($r = -0.42$), and moderate positive correlations with total cholesterol/triglycerides ($r = +0.52$) and serum urea/creatinine ($r = +0.46$). This evidence emphasizes that HbA1c is a strong predictor not just of glycemic control but of systemic complications including anemia, dyslipidemia, and renal dysfunction in this population¹¹.

CONCLUSION

The assessment of T2DM patients in the Garhwal region reveals a significant burden of complications associated with poor disease management and lifestyle factors.

1. Demographically, the high prevalence of obesity (47.5%) is the core challenge, reflecting a major impact of lifestyle changes on disease progression.
2. Clinically, nearly all patients exhibit poor glycemic control (90% raised HbA1c).
3. The most prevalent comorbidities were Dyslipidemia (67.5%), followed by Anemia (52.5%), and early Renal Dysfunction (25%).
4. HbA1c proved to be a strong predictor of complications, correlating significantly with anemia, dyslipidemia, and renal alterations.
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These findings necessitate the implementation of region-specific, integrated diabetes management protocols that focus not only on glucose control but also on weight management, improving lipid profiles, and early screening for renal function to mitigate long-term complications in this rural-hilly population.

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